

Operating high sensitivity measurement apparatus out of equilibrium

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March 31, 2020

Abstract

In this work we present an approach aimed at operating high sensitivity measurement apparatus out of equilibrium with the purpose to enhance their sensitivity. We show, with an experiment, that selective cooling of thermally activated single modes of a mechanical structure, is capable of positively impacting the measurement sensitivity improving significantly the signal-to-noise ratio in the frequency range where the cooling has been applied. More generally, our results suggest that, at difference with the standard way to operate high sensitivity measurement apparatus, i.e. under equilibrium conditions, the cyclical drive-and-relax to equilibrium operation might provide increased sensitivity in selected frequency ranges.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3554277

Introduction

Most of the noise studies, as well as the operational condition of high sensitivity measurements apparatus (e.g. the gravitational wave interferometers), are considered under the assumption that the entire system is time quasi-stationary and at thermal equilibrium. At equilibrium the sensitivity of a measuring apparatus is limited by several environmental (e.g. seismic) and fundamental (e.g. thermal fluctuation) noises. The dynamics of the measuring apparatus and the noise budget determine the spectral shape of equilibrium fluctuations. The ability to detect a signal is influenced by the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), a measure that compares the power of a signal to the power of background noise at a certain frequency. It is clear that, for a fixed signal intensity, to enhance the SNR lowering the noise it is fundamental. Different approaches can be used to reach this goal, from active insulation to damp seismic noise to lower the temperature. Moreover, since the power of the noise is frequency dependant, it is possible to modify the noise spectrum engineering the system's dynamic parameters (e.g. elastic constant or quality factor). Here we present experimental results on an alternative method, that can be combined with standard techniques, operating the measurement apparatus far-from-equilibrium by means of a feedback mechanism[1, 2, 3, 4]. The feedback mechanism is used in a first phase to reduce the noise power in a selected region of the spectrum. Once the feedback is removed the system goes back toward its equilibrium condition. During this last phase we show that is possible to have some benefits enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio. Previous attempts have been carried out through the application of some clever external feedback that could modify the apparatus dynamics in order

to reduce the system response to noise, in desired frequency ranges. One of the first attempts on reducing random thermal fluctuations of electrometer systems by application of a feedback dates to mid of the last century[5]. More recently, a feedback mechanism has been used to reduce the resonance quality factor of a microcantilever[6]. In principle if a measurement apparatus is linearly coupled to the noise and to the signal, then there exists a real-time estimation strategy that reproduces the same measurement record as any arbitrary feedback protocol. In this case any active cooling, stationary or not, does not improve sensitivity over properly chosen data analysis[7]. However we should note that to apply a real-time estimation strategy the system should be linear, its characteristic transfer function should be precisely know, and the system should be in a steady state. In all other cases there might be an advantage on using a feedback mechanism to enhance its sensitivity. In any real physical system with many degrees of freedom these conditions are only approximately met. This is the case for instance of G.W. detectors that in practice do not met the thermodynamic equilibrium conditions[8, 9, 10].

Methodology

A table top interferometer has been setup for testing the potential benefit of the approach. The scheme of the single cavity interferometer used in the experiment is depicted in Fig. 1. An infrared laser ($\lambda=1064\text{ nm}$) is used as light source. The first mirror of the cavity is composed by a semi-reflective Si_3N_4 membrane with a thickness of 30 nm and a window size of $0.5\text{ mm} \times 0.5\text{ mm}$ produced by Norcada (NX10500XS). The light transmitted by the membrane is then reflected by a second mirror with a high coefficient of reflection (BB1-E03 Thorlabs Broadband Dielectric Mirror, reflectivity $> 99\%$). The two beams then recombine and the resulting interference is detected by a photodetector.

Figure 1: Interferometer setup in single cavity configuration. A semi-reflective Si_3N_4 membrane is used as first mirror, part of the light is reflected from the membrane while the transmitted light is reflected from a second mirror placed at distance L from the membrane. The two paths recombine at the photodetector creating interference. The blue path represent the feedback mechanism used to damp the membrane oscillations.

Usually the variable of interest in a setup like the one presented in Fig. 1 is the variation of distance L , between the two mirrors. However another variable in the presented setup plays a role: the fluctuation of the thin membrane, x . As a result the intensity of the light on the photodetector

can be expressed as:

$$I_p = I_0 \cos^2 \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (L + x) \right) \quad (1)$$

In an ideal case the fluctuation of x are null and then the current in the photodetector is only function of the length L . However in reality a small fluctuation of L can be obfuscated by the stochastic motion of the membrane. A reduction of the vibration of the membrane in the spectral region of interest would increase the sensitivity of the detector to a variation of L .

The oscillation of the membrane can be reduced by acting on it with a force which is a function of the readout signal of the interferometer. The applied electrostatic force to damp the membrane oscillation is proportional to signal from the photodetector, band pass filtered, amplified and differentiated. Finally a DC voltage is added to the resulting AC signal in order to be able to push and pull the membrane. The schematic of the feedback mechanism is presented in Fig. 1, blue path. As evident by the description, the feedback mechanisms act as a additional damping term proportional to the displacement of the length $L + x$ in the band filtered region. In the current experiment we have filtered the signal in the region where the oscillation of the membrane is larger, i.e. around the first resonant mode with a bandwidth of 300 Hz. The resulting equation of motion of the membrane, modelled as a single degree of freedom system, is the following:

$$m\ddot{x} = -kx - \gamma\dot{x} - \beta\tilde{V} + \xi(t) \quad (2)$$

where m is the effective mass of the membrane, k the elastic constant, γ the damping constant, \tilde{V} the derivative of the band filtered voltage signal from the photodetector with added the DC bias, β the damping factor of the feedback, proportional to the gain, G , and $\xi(t)$ the noise acting on the system. When the feedback is active (not active) the feedback damping factor is $\beta > 0$ ($\beta = 0$).

The effect of the feedback is presented in Fig. 2 (a) as the power spectral density (PSD) of the voltage from the photodetector when the feedback is active (green curve) and not (red curve). Notice that, in absence of the feedback a clear peak is present around the first resonance frequency of the membrane ($f_0=79.485$ kHz). Once the feedback is activated the peak is reduced by 20 dB. The same data are presented as a time evolution in Fig. 2 (b) where the standard deviation of the voltage at the photodetector is presented. In this case the standard deviation is computed for the signal filtered with a bandwidth of 300 Hz around the resonance peak of the membrane. The green box highlights the condition where the feedback is active. Once the feedback is activated the signal std drops rapidly reaching its minimum value determined by the electronic noise of the measuring system. Once the feedback is deactivated, restoring the original configuration, the signal std increases while the membrane gather energy from the environment. The evolution of the signal standard deviation can be expressed as an exponential time decay (growth) in the form of $A(t) = Ae^{-\frac{t}{\tau_f}}$ ($A(t) = A(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_r}})$) for the falling (rising). The resulting time constant τ for the falling and the rising are $\tau_f=0.045$ s and $\tau_r=0.707$ s respectively. While the rate of falling is determined mostly by the feedback parameters, the raising rate is determined by the quality factor of the membrane, in the experimental setup $Q \sim 1.4e5$.

Figure 2: (a) Power spectral density of thermal noise of the cavity length setting the interferometer sensitivity with (green) and without (red) feedback. (b) Time series of the effect of feedback force applied to the membrane.

To evaluate the potential benefit of the feedback it is interesting to measure the sensitivity of the apparatus in the presence of a variation of L . We should recall that the voltage at the photodiode is the sum of the contribution of L and x . If we activate the feedback when a variation of L is present the force acting on the membrane will try to compensate for this variation as it does with the fluctuation of x . As a consequence the sensitivity of the apparatus can decrease. More interesting is the scenario where a transient signal altering the length L appears when the feedback is switched off. In this case we can evaluate the signal to noise ratio (SNR) while the system goes back to equilibrium. For mimicking an external signal we modify the position of the mirror by means of a piezoelectric actuator with a periodic displacement at a frequency near the resonant frequency of the membrane, within the Q of the resonance, and an amplitude small enough to be masked by the oscillation of the membrane at equilibrium ($SNR \approx 0.3$).

To evaluate the SNR evolution we have injected the signal just after the feedback is removed. The standard deviation of the voltage produced by the photodetector with and without the signal are presented in Fig. 3 (a): if the signal is present the overall standard deviation is higher than the one when only noise is present as expected. However the ratio between the two tends to decrease as time increases. This is more evident in Fig. 3 (b) where the SNR is presented as function of time. While the power of the signal remains constant in time, the power of the noise increases with a rate determined by the time constant τ_r . As a consequence the SNR decreases with time reaching a minimum value when the system is at equilibrium. The last value obtained for the SNR is also the one relative to a system where the feedback is not used. In the presented experiment is evident that for a non negligible portion of time the SNR is increased by a factor five respect to without the use of the feedback, enhancing substantially the sensitivity of the detector.

Figure 3: (a) Time evolution of the detected signal std with (blue) and without (black) injected signal. The periodic signal to be detected is injected as soon as the feedback is turned off. (b) SNR evaluated for a fixed amplitude signal as a function of time after the feedback is deactivated and the signal is present.

Feedback application strategy

We have seen that operating the apparatus out of equilibrium can improve the sensitivity of the device. However, while the feedback is active the sensitivity of the apparatus can decrease considerably and thus during this phase the instrument should be considered unusable. Because of this it is important to conceive a strategy to optimize the performance of the device, trying to maximize the usable time and at the same time enhancing the performance in terms of SNR. In a cyclic application of the feedback mechanism we can define the duty cycle as $1 - t_f/T_C$, where t_f is the duration of feedback application and T_C the total duration of the cycle. We can thus achieve the same duty cycle with different combinations of t_f and T_C . Furthermore, even if t_f is small enough to not reach the noise floor in a single cycle, since usually τ_f is smaller than τ_r , after a given number of cycles the system reaches a steady state condition. A cartoon of this condition is depicted in Fig. 4 for two different duty cycles.

Figure 4: Cartoon of time evolution of the signal standard deviation for two different duty cycle. After few cycle of feedback application the system reaches a steady state.

In the steady state conditions, the average noise level during the rising condition sets the performance of the strategy (green lines in Fig. 4). The lower the noise, the higher the SNR for a fixed signal amplitude is. For such a reason it is interesting to evaluate the average noise level as a function of t_f and T_C . In Fig. 5 we report this metric for different values of T_C as a function of the duty cycle. In this case the level of noise without the application of a feedback strategy is $\approx 0.7e - 5V$, slightly higher than data presented above. This discrepancy is due to different session of measurement.

Symbols represent experimental values while continuous lines came from a simple model considering the measured time constants for falling and rising. The saturation near duty cycle 100% is due to an activation lag of the feedback.

Figure 5: Effect of feedback as function of duty cycle of feedback activation and total duration of the cycle. The symbols represent the average standard deviation of the thermal noise around the resonance peak during the period in which the feedback is not active as function of the duty cycle of the feedback. Different colors represent different total window time. Symbols are relative to experiment while continuous lines refer to data from the model.

As expected, for a fixed cycle duration, decreasing the duty cycle the average noise decreases and thus the SNR increases. Similarly, given a duty cycle, decreasing the time cycle duration increases the performance. The cycle duration and the required duty cycle should be chosen depending on the phenomena to be observed and the controllability of the signal to be detected. As mentioned above, the application of the feedback should not coincide with the signal. Therefore, while the duty cycle should be as large as possible, at the same time the duration of the signal should be shorter than the cycle windows making large time cycles preferred. For these reasons a trade-off between these parameters is required and depends on the scientific and technological aspects.

Conclusions

In this work we have presented experimental results showing that periodic driving a measuring system out-of-equilibrium can enhance its sensitivity during the recovering phase. This can be done by cooling via feedback control improving the signal to noise ratio for transient signals shorter than the period time length. The same results can be obtained by applying a real-time estimation strategy if the system is linear, its transfer characteristic is precisely known, and the system is in a steady state. In any other case there might be an advantage, depending on the relaxation time of the system and on the time scale of the signals to be detected.

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